

Research Article

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**Methodological Precedence in Health Tech: An Exploratory Case on the Necessity of
Descriptive and Inferential Statistics to Validate Inputs for ML/Big Data
Epidemiological Models**

Marco Rocchetti

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

University of Bologna, 40126, Italy

marco.rocchetti@unibo.it

ORCID: 0000-0003-1264-8595

Abstract: The adoption of sophisticated analytical tools, including Machine Learning (ML) and massive data processing, has accelerated health research. However, a foundational principle asserts that the rigor of these complex methods is dependent on the integrity and validity of the underlying statistical design. We posit that advanced analyses, particularly in epidemiology, must be subsequent to the rigorous verification of basic methodological coherence. This study uses an exploratory case to demonstrate a crucial cautionary principle: complex models amplify, rather than correct, severe methodological flaws. To demonstrate this, we apply standard descriptive and inferential statistical methods (Z-tests, Confidence Intervals, and t-tests) alongside established national epidemiological benchmarks to a recently published cohort study on vaccine outcomes and psychiatric events. Through this approach, we expose multiple, statistically irreconcilable paradoxes within the source data, including implausible incidence rates and profound baseline group imbalances. These findings, proven by inferential statistical evidence, demonstrate that the observed effects (e.g., contradictory Hazard Ratios) are not biological but are mathematical artifacts stemming from uncorrected selection and classification biases in the cohort construction. Our analysis serves as a robust demonstration that the validity of any conclusion drawn from subsequent advanced ML or statistical modeling sourced from health data rests entirely on first passing the test of basic epidemiological consistency.

Keywords: Biostatistics; ML/Big Data Precedence; Descriptive and Inferential Statistics, Computational Epidemiology, Selection Bias

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1. Introduction

The modern era of medical research is defined by an escalating reliance on Big Data platforms and Machine/Deep Learning (ML/DL) algorithms [1]. These technologies, ranging from neural networks for medical image analysis to predictive models for population health, promise to uncover subtle associations and forecast patient outcomes with high precision. The prevailing narrative often suggests that the complexity of the computational approach inherently guarantees the robustness and reliability of the conclusions, creating a dangerous methodological inversion where complex modeling precedes basic data validation [2, 3]. In fact, research demonstrates that simpler models, when properly specified, can yield identical or more stable results than overly complex computational methods [4, 5].

However, a core principle of data science remains immutable and should be the *sine qua non* for any complex analysis: the outcome of any processing, regardless of its computational sophistication, is ultimately constrained by the quality and design integrity of the input data. A flawed methodological foundation, particularly in medical cohort construction or case definition, will not be corrected by the power of complex statistics or ML/DL. Instead, the complexity may mask and amplify the underlying bias. This is why the application of ML/DL and Big Data tools in health research must be rigorously conditioned on the initial validation of the cohort through descriptive and inferential statistical methods and the consistency of its observed epidemiological metrics.

For example, in retrospective observational studies utilizing large administrative databases (such as National Health Service cohorts), the crucial challenge lies in achieving covariate balance between comparison groups. Failure to correct for intrinsic, large differences in baseline characteristics (like age, comorbidity status, and health-seeking behavior) introduces severe selection and misclassification bias. The resulting statistical metrics, such as Hazard Ratios (HRs), would then reflect this baseline disparity rather than any true biological effect.

In this paper, we leverage the power of basic descriptive and rigorous inferential statistics (e.g., Z-tests and t-tests) alongside established national epidemiological benchmarks to expose a severe, uncorrected selection bias in the cohort construction of a population-based study [6] investigating the association between an intervention (COVID-19 vaccination) and psychiatric outcomes in a South Korean cohort. Our objective is not to perform a complex re-analysis, but to prove that simple methodological scrutiny is the definitive test for validity, a prerequisite that must be satisfied before any subsequent ML/DL or predictive analysis is meaningful.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: The Materials and Methods section (Section 2) details our consistency check approach, including the use of specific inferential statistical tests. In Section 3, we present the three major epidemiological paradoxes observed in the scrutinized data, which were derived from checks rooted in basic statistical epidemiology. Had these simple consistency checks not been applied, the data could have proceeded to advanced modeling, inevitably producing an invalid model for subsequent clinical inference. Section 4 discusses how advanced models like ML/DL would fail catastrophically on such flawed data, emphasizing the urgent necessity of basic yet robust covariate balancing techniques. Finally, Section 5 provides a summary conclusion of our finding.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Data Sources

The data analyzed in this report are entirely sourced from the published literature, specifically from the reported incidence rates and baseline characteristics extracted directly from the primary study under examination [6]. This study utilized administrative data to compare outcomes over a three-month follow-up period between a vaccinated group and an unvaccinated control group. Given the nature of the case study, which investigates the association between COVID-19 vaccination and adverse psychiatric events, it is necessary to perform preliminary data validation and calculations to ensure the integrity of subsequent inferences. This analysis will focus specifically on key psychiatric outcomes, specifically: 1) Schizophrenia (ICD-10 F20-F29), 2) Bipolar Disorder (ICD-10 F31), and 3) Anxiety Disorder (ICD-10 F41.x). Instead, the epidemiological benchmarks used for comparison are derived from robust, independent national studies focused on the South Korean population (subject of the

investigated case), which provide validated annual prevalence and incidence rates for the psychiatric conditions studied [7, 8, 9].

2.2 Descriptive Statistics

First, we list and explain, here, the descriptive statistics methods, and their corresponding formulas, used for basic epidemiological checks on the study data under scrutiny.

2.2.1 Calculation of Epidemiological Consistency Metrics

To assess the validity of the reported incidence rates and Hazard Ratios (HRs), we applied standard statistical methods based on consistency checks and known relationships between epidemiological measures. To begin, all national annual incidence and prevalence rates were normalized to the equivalent three-month period and to the per 10,000 population scale used in the primary study [6] for direct comparison using the conversion formula for annual incidence $I(Annual)$ to estimated quarterly incidence $I(Quarterly)$ expressed as:

$$I(Quarterly) = I(Annual) / 4 . \quad (1)$$

2.2.2 Calculation of Expected Upper Bounds

For Anxiety Disorders particularly, the reported 12-month prevalence $P(Annual)$ was used to establish an absolute theoretical upper limit for the incidence over three months [9]. Since in computational epidemiology the *incidence* (new cases) must be lower than its *prevalence* (total existing cases), the quarterly fraction of the national prevalence serves as the maximum plausible quarterly incidence ($P(Quarterly_max)$) as shown below:

$$P(Quarterly_max) = P(Annual) / 4 . \quad (2)$$

2.2.3 Consistency Checks on Hazard Ratios (HRs)

The Hazard Ratio (HR) is the ratio of the hazard rates between the vaccinated $H(\text{Vaccinated})$ and unvaccinated $H(\text{Unvaccinated})$ groups. The consistency check examines the simultaneous occurrence of highly disparate HRs (e.g., $\text{HR} \gg 1$ and $\text{HR} \ll 1$) for different chronic conditions within the same non-adjusted cohort, to assess if the effect is biological or an artefact due to baseline bias.

2.3 Inferential Statistics

After basic descriptive statistics, we list here the inferential statistics methods necessary to develop rigorous hypothesis testing procedures that add inferential confirmation (or simply rejection) to the validity hypotheses of the initial data coming from study [6]. The methods are explained succinctly, but with a listing of the corresponding null and alternative hypotheses [10].

2.3.1 One-Sample Z-Test for Schizophrenia Incidence

The purpose of this inferential test is to statistically assess the validity of the Schizophrenia incidence rate reported in [6] for the vaccinated group, by comparing it against established national epidemiological benchmarks, thereby testing the Null Hypothesis of methodological consistency. The analysis will rely on the following key data and metrics:

1. Observed Rate (i.e., $P(\text{Obs})$): Extracted directly from [6], showing the 3-month Schizophrenia incidence rate in the vaccinated cohort.
2. Benchmark Rate (i.e., $P(\text{Bench})$): Derived from the robust national registry study in [7], which establishes the expected annual incidence for Schizophrenia in South Korea. This annual rate is normalized to a 3-month (quarterly) period.
3. Sample Size (N): The exact size of the vaccinated cohort, $N(\text{Vac})$, as reported in [6].

A summary of these figures is reported in Table 1 below.

Metric	Value (3-month rate/proportion)	Source/Reference	Calculation of Cases
Observed Rate $P(Obs)$	$0.51 / 10,000 =$ 0.000051	Kim HJ et al. [6] (Vaccinated Cohort)	$1,718,999 \times$ $0.000051 \approx 88$
Benchmark Rate $P(Bench)$	$\sim 2.1 / 10,000 =$ 0.00021	Cho et al. [7] (National Incidence Range: 2.0-2.2/10,000 annually, normalized / 4)	$1,718,999 \times$ $0.00021 \approx 361$
Cohort Size (N)	1,718,999	Kim et al. [6] (Vaccinated Cohort)	-

Table 1: Data inputs required to compare the observed 3-month incidence proportion of Schizophrenia in the vaccinated cohort (Kim et al. [6]) against the national epidemiological benchmark (Cho et al. [7]).

In this case, the test of interest specifically aims to detect a non-plausible *deficit* in observed cases, making it a one-tailed Z-test which can be defined as follows:

- Null Hypothesis (H_0). The observed Schizophrenia incidence proportion in the vaccinated cohort $P(Vac)$ is equal to or greater than the national benchmark proportion $P(Bench)$. This assumes methodological consistency: $H_0: P(Vac) \geq P(Bench)$.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H_1). The observed 3-month schizophrenia incidence rate in the vaccinated cohort is significantly lower than the national benchmark rate, suggesting uncorrected bias, $H_1: P(Vac) < P(Bench)$.

At this point a correct statistical test is needed to decide H_0 vs H_1 . This is the Z-score test statistic which is calculated using the standard formula for comparing a sample proportion to a known population proportion: $Z = \frac{P(Obs) - P(Bench)}{\sqrt{(P(Bench)(1 - P(Bench)))/N}}$.

2.3.2 Confidence Interval Calculation for Bipolar Disorder Incidence

The objective is to establish the statistical precision and plausible range of the observed 3-month Bipolar Disorder (BD) incidence rate reported in the unvaccinated control cohort of [6]. This precision will then be compared against the external 12-month national prevalence rate from [8] to test for methodological consistency. This time,

the idea is to use fromal statistical hypothesis testing from inferential statistics to corroborate (or reject) the validation activity begun with simpler techniques of descriptive statistics. We initiate this analysis focusing on the unvaccinated control group, where the anomalous BD incidence rate was observed, as reported in Table 2 below.

Metric	Value (Proportion or Count)	Source/Context
Observed Incidence Proportion (P)	0.000139 (from 1.39/10,000)	Extracted from [6] (Unvaccinated Control Group, 3-month incidence).
Prevalence Benchmark ($P(Bench)$)	0.000106 (from 1.06/10,000)	Extracted from [8] (National 12-month Prevalence for similar conditions).
Control Cohort Size (N)	308,354	Size of the Unvaccinated Control Group reported in [6].
Observed Cases (O)	≈ 43	Calculated from $N \times P$

Table 2: Data inputs comparing the 3-month observed BD incidence proportion (P) in the unvaccinated control cohort [6] against the 12-month BD national prevalence benchmark ($P(Bench)$) [8].

In this case, we will use the Wald method to calculate the 95% Confidence Interval for the observed BD incidence proportion (P). The formula for the 95% Confidence Interval for the proportion is: $CI(95\%) = P \pm Z_{\alpha/2} \times SE$, where P is the observed BD incidence proportion (0.000139); $Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$ (i.e., the critical Z-value for a 95% CI) and SE (the Standard Error) which in turn can be calculated as $\sqrt{\frac{(1-P)P}{N}}$. At this point, the inferential test involves checking the relative position of the 12-month BD prevalence benchmark ($P(Bench)$) within the calculated 95% CI of the 3-month BD incidence (P). If the benchmark is statistically consistent with the observed incidence rate, it will fall within the calculated CI.

2.3.3 Two-Sample Independent t -Test for Covariate Balance (Mean Age)

The purpose of this inferential test is to check a more general condition that could affect the representativeness of a given cohort. Essentially, we want to determine if the compared cohorts (in [6]) were statistically equivalent on a critical confounding variable, *Mean Age*, prior to the intervention. Establishing this baseline balance is a necessary prerequisite for valid causal inference in non-randomized studies. In the end, following this way, it will be possible to verify if the scrutinized study [6] yields valid or contradictory HRs. In this latter case, this would reflect the confounding effect of these pre-existing differences, rather than the biological effect of the vaccination

intervention. We begin this kind of analysis utilizing the baseline statistics reported in [6] for the Mean Age of the two comparison groups reported in Table 3.

Metric	Value	Source/Context ([6])
Vaccinated Mean Age ($\bar{X}(Vac)$)	54.67 years	Reported mean age for the vaccinated group.
Vaccinated SD ($SD(Vac)$)	16.26	Reported standard deviation for the vaccinated group.
Vaccinated Cohort Size ($N(Vac)$)	1,718,999	Cohort size used for the t-test.
Non-Vaccinated Mean Age ($\bar{X}(NonVac)$)	44.18 years	Reported mean age for the non-vaccinated group.
Non-Vaccinated ($SD(NonVac)$)	16.2	Reported standard deviation for the non-vaccinated group.
Non-Vaccinated Cohort Size ($N(NonVac)$)	308,354	Cohort size used for the t-test.

Table 3: Empirical baseline characteristics (Mean Age and Standard Deviation) derived from [6], used to test the assumption of covariate balance between the Vaccinated and Non-Vaccinated sub-cohorts.

We use Welch's Independent Samples t-Test to compare the means of the two cohorts. Specifically, we structure the following hypothesis test:

- Null Hypothesis ($H0$). There is no statistically significant difference in the mean age between the Vaccinated and Unvaccinated cohorts (i.e., the groups are balanced for age): $H0: \bar{X}(Vac) = \bar{X}(NonVac)$
- Alternative Hypothesis ($H1$). There is a statistically significant difference in the mean age between the two cohorts (i.e., the groups are unbalanced): $\bar{X}(Vac) \neq \bar{X}(NonVac)$.

The final t-test statistic is calculated as: $t = (\bar{X}(Vac) - \bar{X}(NonVac)) / \sqrt{\frac{SD(Vac)^2}{N(Vac)} + \frac{SD(NonVac)^2}{N(NonVac)}}$.

3. Results

The application of basic consistency metrics to the published data of [6] reveals three fundamental statistical paradoxes that challenge the core findings of that study. If these statistical epidemiological checks, which highlighted the three paradoxes discussed below, had not been performed first, any subsequent analyses or inferences would have been invalid, contradictory, or, at a minimum, irrelevant.

3.1 Paradox I: Implausible Protective Effect for Schizophrenia

The study [6] reports a Hazard Ratio (HR) of 0.231 for the development of Schizophrenia (ICD-10: F20-F29) in the vaccinated group compared to the unvaccinated control group. Obviously, an HR below 1.0 would suggest a protective effect, and HR of 0.231 is interpreted as an approximately 77% reduction in the risk of developing Schizophrenia ($1 - 0.231$). This is the first paradox: there is no biological or clinical justification for a COVID-19 vaccine to confer such a profound, immediate protective effect against a chronic, neurodevelopmental disorder like Schizophrenia. To understand the mathematical source of this implausible finding, we must compare the incidence rates used to calculate this HR against known epidemiological benchmarks like in Table 4 below.

Condition	Group	Reported Incidence [6] (per 10,000 over 3 mo)	Crude Ratio (Vac / Unvac)	National Benchmark [7] (Quarterly Range per 10,000)
Schizophrenia	Unvaccinated Control	1.98	Not applicable	2.0 - 2.2
	Vaccinated (High-Risk)	0.51	0.257	2.0 - 2.2

Table 4: Reported and Benchmark quarterly incidence rates for Schizophrenia (ICD-10 F20-F29), illustrating severe cohort selection bias.

The reported HR of 0.231 is extremely close to the crude ratio of the incidence rates ($0.51 / 1.98$, approx. 0.257). The small difference exists because the HR is derived from a Cox regression model which incorporates time-to-event data and slight adjustments, whereas 0.257 is a simple rate ratio. Unfortunately, both values signify the same magnitude of disparity. Nonetheless, the unequivocal proof of the methodological error is the incidence rate observed in the Vaccinated cohort (0.51 per 10,000). In fact, this rate is:

1. Nearly four times lower than the Unvaccinated Control group (1.98).
2. Drastically below the stable national epidemiological benchmark (2.0 - 2.2), which represents the expected rate for the general population.

Given that the vaccinated group was, on average, older and less healthy at baseline, its incidence rate should logically be *higher* than the control group's rate, or at least comparable to the national benchmark. The observed severe deficit of new Schizophrenia cases in this cohort is the direct result of an uncorrected selection or misclassification bias at baseline. Specifically, it indicates that individuals with pre-existing (prevalent) chronic Schizophrenia were systematically excluded or miscategorized from the vaccinated cohort, artificially lowering its observed incidence and mathematically forcing the resulting Hazard Ratio to be an implausibly low artifact.

We pass now, for a further confirmaton, to the use of the inferential statistics with the statistical tests introduced earlier in Section 2.3.1. Starting from the definition of Z and substituting the real cohort data and benchmark values we get: $Z = 0.000051 - 0.00021 / \sqrt{0.00021(1 - 0.00021/N1,718,999)} \approx -14.39$.

The resultant Z-Score of approx. -14.39 is an extreme value that corresponds to a p -value $\ll 0.000001$. Consequently, the Null Hypothesis (H_0) is decisively rejected, yielding the following consideration. This inferential result statistically validates the presence of the methodological flaw described in Paradox I, in particular:

- a. Quantitative Disparity: Based on the national registry data from [7] ($P(Bench)$), the cohort of 1,718,999 individuals should have yielded approximately 361 new cases of Schizophrenia over three months (the expected number). However, the study [6] reports an observed rate that corresponds to only approximately 88 cases.
- b. Conclusive Finding: The Z-test confirms that this relevant 75% deficit (361 expected vs. 88 observed) is statistically impossible to attribute to random chance. It is definitive evidence that the vaccinated cohort was not a representative sample of the South Korean population at baseline.
- c. Methodological Error: This outcome is consistent with a severe selection bias or misclassification error where individuals with pre-existing (prevalent) Schizophrenia were systematically excluded or miscategorized from the vaccinated group. This failure to achieve epidemiological consistency at baseline is what mathematically forced the Hazard Ratio (HR) to become the implausible protective

artifact (HR=0.231), invalidating the study's conclusions regardless of the complexity of subsequent statistical models, hence closing this issue.

3.2 Paradox II: Epidemiological Impossibility for Bipolar Disorder

An absolute inconsistency arises when comparing the reported incidence rate for Bipolar Disorder (BD) in the control group to national prevalence data, as shown in Table 5.

Condition	Group	Metric	Reported Value [6] (per 10,000)	National Benchmark [8] (12-Month Prevalence per 10,000)
Bipolar Disorder	Unvaccinated Control	3-month Incidence	1.39	Not applicable
BPD (Similar Severity)	National Population	12-month Prevalence	Not applicable	1.06

Table 5: Comparison of reported 3-Month Bipolar Disorder incidence against national 12-Month prevalence, revealing epidemiological impossibility (Paradox II)

Here the paradox can be explained as follows. By definition, the *incidence* (new cases over three months) of a severe chronic condition (BD) cannot exceed the *prevalence* (total existing cases) of a similar condition over a longer period (a full year). The reported three-month incidence of BD (1.39) in the control group [6] is statistically impossible as it exceeds the national 12-month prevalence of a condition of similar severity (1.06) [8]. In simpler words, the anomaly is given by a fundamental mathematical and statistical impossibility: the reported value of 1.39 (the incidence, i.e., the new cases of Bipolar Disorder over only 3 months) is higher than the entire national prevalence of 1.06 (which represents the total existing cases, both old and new, over a full 12-month period), violating the epidemiological principle that quarterly incidence cannot exceed the annual prevalence of the same condition in a stable population, This invalidates the derived HR of 0.672.

If we pass, as usually in our analysis, to inferential statistics, we can now calculate the figure announced in previous Section 2.3.2. Hence, the calculation of the standard Error (*SE*) yields $SE = \sqrt{\frac{0.000139(1-0.000139)}{308,354}} = 0.00002124$, while the calculation of the Margin of error (*ME*) achieves $ME = 1.96 \times 0.00002124 \approx 0.0000416$.

Now, we have all the ingredients to approach the calculation of the 95% CI limits per 10,000. In fact, The CI can be calculated as 1.39 ± 0.416 per 10,000, where its lower limit is 0.974 and its upper limit is 1.806, both per 10,000. At this time, the 95% Confidence Interval for the 3-month BD incidence is straightforward: [0.974, 1.806] per 10,000. We have arrived at the point where also the inferential results confirm the severity of the methodological flaw of Paradox II, in fact:

- i. Observed CI vs. Benchmark: The calculated CI for the 3-month incidence rate (new cases) is [0.974, 1.806]. The 12-month Prevalence Benchmark (1.06/10,000) falls within this interval.
- ii. The Paradox Confirmed: The inclusion of the 12-month prevalence value inside the CI of the 3-month incidence rate, while statistically allowed, is epidemiologically nonsensical. It means the statistical estimate for the rate of new cases over 90 days is so high that it is statistically compatible with the total rate of all existing cases over 365 days.

In closing this Section, this statistically verified anomaly supports the core argument where the observed incidence rate of 1.39 per 10,000 population of [6] is an extreme and highly improbable estimate. It points strongly to a massive misclassification error where a significant number of prevalent (existing) BD cases were erroneously identified and counted as incident (new) cases in the unvaccinated control cohort. This structural error consequently invalidates the derived Hazard Ratio (HR = 0.672).

3.3 Paradox III: Contradictory HRs for Anxiety and more Common Disorders

The third and final paradox is as follows. The cohort selection bias not only creates falsely low HRs (protection, Paradox I) but simultaneously generates falsely high HRs for common disorders, such as Anxiety Disorders. The study [6] reports an HR = 1.439 for these common disorders, suggesting a detrimental effect of COVID-19 vaccination. The simultaneous presence of $HR \ll 1$ (suggesting protection for chronic disorders) and $HR \gg 1$ (suggesting harm for common disorders) within the same uncorrected cohort is the definitive mathematical evidence that the observed effect is not biological, but a direct confirmation of the underlying uncorrected baseline disparity. The bias manifests differently across distinct pathologies based on the baseline prevalence in the two cohorts.

Moving, now, to inferential statistics and hypothesis testing as anticipated earlier in Section 2.3.3, and substituting the empirical mean age, standard deviations, and cohort sizes into the t-test formula, we achieve what follows:

1. Mean Difference (Numerator): $54.67 - 44.18 = 10.49$ years,
2. Standard Error (Denominator): $\sqrt{\frac{16.26^2}{1,718,999} + \frac{16.28^2}{308,354}} = 0.03183$,
3. Calculated t-score: $t = 10.49 / 0.03183 = 329.58$.

In conclusion, the calculated t-score is 329.58, but, given the massive sample size, this result corresponds to an infinitesimally small *p-value* ($\ll 0.000001$). After all, this formally validates the finding reported in [6] itself (*p-value* < 0.001), but the Null Hypothesis *H0* is overwhelmingly rejected. The consequence of this rejection confirms the methodological weakness underpinning the contradictory findings of [6], specifically:

- I. **Statistical Proof of Imbalance:** The t-test confirms that the two cohorts were severely and statistically non-randomly unbalanced on age, differing by over 10 years on average (54.67 vs. 44.18). This disparity is a heavy evidence of the selection bias arising from using simple random sampling on an administrative database.
- II. **Causation of Paradox III:** This proven imbalance explains the contradictory Hazard Ratios (HRs). Since the Vaccinated group is significantly older and more comorbid (as indicated by the high mean age), it has a naturally higher baseline risk for conditions correlated with age, such as Anxiety/Stress Disorders (HR $\gg 1$). Conversely, its low incidence for Schizophrenia (HR $\ll 1$) is due to the non-random exclusion of prevalent cases (as confirmed by the Z-Test for Paradox I).

4. Discussion

The analysis presented here, leveraging basic descriptive and rigorous inferential statistics (specifically the Z-test for Paradox I and II, and the t-test for Paradox III) and established epidemiological reference points, unequivocally demonstrates that the findings of study [6] are statistically unreliable and would invalidate any medical inferences if they were considered without a prior statistical check. It is a plausible hypothesis that the study's core methodological weakness lies in the control cohort construction, selected via random sampling (50% of unvaccinated individuals), an inadequate approach in retrospective administrative data studies. This random selection, in fact, fails to account for the vast, intrinsic differences between individuals who choose to be

vaccinated (often older, with more comorbidities, and exhibiting higher health-seeking behavior) and those who do not. Hence the following further considerations are in order.

4.1 Amplification of Bias by Advanced Modeling

This case raises the critical question of what would have transpired if researchers had immediately moved past the initial biased cohort construction and applied sophisticated inference tools like machine/deep learning (ML/DL) algorithms. The answer is alarming: ML/DL models do not correct fundamental selection bias; they simply automate and amplify it. For example, consider the points that follow.

Reinforced Misclassification (The Schizophrenia Case): The ML model would be trained to predict the outcome based on the feature space of the highly biased cohorts. Since the feature "Vaccinated" is artificially correlated with a low Schizophrenia rate (due to prevalent cases being excluded from that group, Paradox I), an ML model would learn this false association. When deployed in a clinical setting, such a model would falsely flag vaccinated status as a protective factor for Schizophrenia, leading to incorrect clinical risk stratification.

Over-Sensitivity to Noise (The Bipolar Case): The highly complex algorithms, designed to find subtle patterns, would attempt to find a non-linear relationship explaining the epidemiologically impossible high BD incidence in the control group (Paradox II). The model might latch onto an irrelevant feature (e.g., zip code, specific primary care physician) that happens to be correlated with the data-entry error, yielding a complex, yet meaningless, "explanation" that adds zero predictive value but increases computational cost and model opacity.

Falsely Prioritized Features: The model would assign significant weight to the treatment variable (vaccination) because of the strong, albeit artificial, signal it carries (HR=0.231 for Schizophrenia, HR=1.439 for Anxiety). The model's complex feature importance metrics would mislead the investigator into believing the intervention is the primary driver of the outcome, ignoring the foundational methodological flaw that created the signal. This is a classic example of *garbage in, gospel out*, where the complexity of the output lends undeserved credence to flawed inputs.

In essence, by skipping the basic consistency check, we would risk creating high-performance predictive models that are robustly and confidently predicting an artifact.

4.2 Necessity of Covariate Balancing

The observed anomalies strongly suggest a failure to properly define prevalent cases at baseline, leading to systematic misclassification. This methodological failure requires correction that ML and Big Data analyses cannot provide post hoc. We propose that any valid analysis of this data must employ a statistically robust procedure, such as *Propensity Score Matching* (PSM) [11], for example. PSM is specifically designed for retrospective studies to achieve a true covariate balance, minimizing the effect of confounding factors between the groups. The reliance on complex HR calculations without first establishing this foundational balance has allowed a severe methodological error to propagate, resulting in findings that contradict basic epidemiological knowledge. This case study highlights that sophisticated statistical models are no substitute for rigorous study design and proper cohort construction.

5. Conclusion

This analysis critically evaluated a population-based health study by returning to the fundamental principles of epidemiological consistency, a necessary precursor to advanced analytical methods like Big Data and Machine Learning (ML) [1, 2]. By systematically applying descriptive and inferential statistical methods (Z-tests, Confidence Intervals, and t-tests) to the study's reported rates and baseline characteristics [6], and juxtaposing them against established national benchmarks [7, 8, 9], we discovered multiple, severe statistical paradoxes. These contradictions, including a statistically implausible protective effect for a chronic mental health condition (Schizophrenia), an epidemiologically impossible incidence rate (Bipolar Disorder), and a massive baseline covariate imbalance (proven by the t-test), conclusively establish the presence of uncontrolled selection and misclassification biases in the cohort construction. The derived Hazard Ratios (HRs) are therefore numerical artifacts of this deep methodological flaw, rather than reflections of a genuine biological association. Our investigation serves as a strong admonition that the inherent complexity of computational analysis, far from correcting poor data quality, will invariably amplify and obscure underlying structural errors, especially when ML and Deep Learning (DL) models are deployed on such severely compromised inputs. Consequently, the utility and reliability of any Big Data-driven health research are strictly conditional upon the prior successful implementation of robust study designs and preliminary inferential statistical validation to ensure the input data is fundamentally sound and epidemiologically consistent.

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Contributions

MR conducted the data analysis, conceptualized the statistical arguments, and wrote the paper.

Corresponding author

Correspondence to Marco Rocchetti: marco.rocchetti@unibo.it.

Competing interests

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Data Availability

The data presented here is either included directly or was extracted from the referenced documents. All calculations are easily reproducible based on the definitions provided

Ethics approval and consent to participate

This study uses publicly available, aggregated data that contains no private information. Therefore, ethical approval is not required

Generative AI statement

The author declares that no Gen AI was used in the creation of this manuscript